

EXPRESSION OF RELIGIOUS VALUES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PAREMIOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10608657>

Abstract. This thesis deals with a structural-semantic analysis of the language structure of English proverbs. At the same time, the ponder of all perspectives of sayings is one of the most important assignments in the field of paremiology. When examining the comparative perspectives of sayings, it is incomprehensible not to center on their linguocultural aspects. In this way, we attempt to see the similitudes and contrasts between the proverbs within the dialects we are studying, the one-of-a-kind culture, and the attitude of the individuals who speak that language.

Proverbs as paremiological units are studied in linguistics, linguodidactics and the methodology of language teaching. Comparative study of Proverbs of two or more languages allows us to identify similarities and differences that contribute to building the most scientifically sound method of teaching a non-native language. Since ancient times, the Paremiological Fund has interested scientists. Aristotle was the first to classify and systematize Proverbs and sayings (paremias). He noted that paremias are elements of the old philosophy that have survived because of their brevity. Proverbs are worldly wisdom, spiritual wealth, and cultural heritage of the people, proven by centuries of experience. As the author of the vast collection of Russian Proverbs and sayings, the famous linguist and writer V.I. Dahl, "proverb... is not composed, but is born itself". For the research work of scientists of various specialties — paremiologists, linguists, literary critics, folklorists, ethnographers, and others, the world of Proverbs and sayings is a fertile field. This is quite reasonable, because the proverb, despite the small volume, can be considered in various aspects of the study. For a relatively young branch of the science of language - the linguistics of the text, the proverb is of great interest as a completely complete (in semantic and structural relations) text. Because different Proverbs of the same language and even related and unrelated languages can belong to the same logical type and denote the same situation, they are directly related to logical semantics and semiotics. Because a proverb is a certain syntactic unit — a sentence, the formal structure of a proverb must be studied by grammar. Regarding Proverbs, in recent years, there are ambiguous, and at times even polar points of view. Thus, one of the founders of modern paremiology G.A.

Permyakov believes that the imagery and external design of the proverb, reflecting its ethnographic and ethnogenetic realities, do not seem to be the main thing that characterizes it. In his opinion, the main thing is that the main content of the proverb is determined by logical constructions, and "Proverbs and sayings are signs of situations or certain relations between things". [1]

Historians find in proverbs the customs of antiquity and echoes of ancient events; lawyers see in proverbs the reflection of customary law; the ethnographer, thanks to proverbs, get an idea of the character of already disappeared customs and orders; philologists through proverbs try to understand the features and structure of popular thinking; linguists see in proverbs the most valuable material for the study of the nature and laws of human speech". [2] It is quite obvious that a deep and comprehensive analysis of Proverbs is impossible without the broad involvement of the mentioned Sciences, but on the contrary, the study of Proverbs is extremely useful, important, and necessary for the development of these sciences.

Sapir emphasizes that the vocabulary of a language is created by the physical and social atmosphere of humanity. And based on this theory, we can cite language as part of culture. He also believes that the language that underlies every culture should never be studied in isolation from culture and humanity uses language to express every aspect of culture. V. Telia, as a linguist and folklorist, emphasizes the role of paremiology in the connection of culture with language. He said that while language represents an entire culture, there is no doubt that the field of paremiology can beautifully and deeply express the culture of a people who speak the language. This is because linguoculturology is a mixture of languages and cultures. Thus, proverbs as one of the most active tools in the expression of folk culture are becoming one of the most important topics in the process of linguoculturological research in linguistics today. It is used as the main object of many researches. Telia calls proverbs "direct cultural signs" and believes that they are factors that reflect the culture of the people as a whole. Each proverb, in his opinion, is a mirror that can fully reflect the way of life of the people concisely. He says in one of his works: "After having described the interaction between language, culture, and proverbs, it also seems important to mention how culture is implemented through language. Each culture has a set of proverbs that could be defined as basic, when they enter the lexicon and the language, they may act as "direct cultural signs". This means that while every word that exists in the language of a people is expressed in the language, the proverbs of a certain people are represented by the words of that people by the

representatives of that nation with the peculiarities of that nation, the method of construction. Many scholars including Henl P, E. Sepir, G.G. Morian, and C Kramsh address issues such as the relationship between culture and language. Concerning the linguoculturological qualities of proverbs, Nida believes that it is natural for scholars to study the language and culture of the people directly when studying proverbs. English: "The nearer the Church, the farther from God" translates to Uzbek - the closer you get to the church, the farther you are from God. This is expressed in the Uzbek proverb: "He does not abandon the five daily prayers and does not distinguish between the forbidden and the forbidden." The word "Church" in the English proverb means "church" in Uzbek translation. The word "church" is not originally Uzbek, but Uzbek is a term borrowed from other languages. The church is a place where people of Christianity perform their religious rites. In Uzbek, the word "mosque" is equivalent to this word. If we look at the religions of the two peoples, the majority of the Uzbek people are Muslims, and the British people are almost Christians. In Christianity, the church is considered the holiest place for Christians, and as mentioned above, Christian customs and traditions are held there. We can't say a church is a place for Muslims to perform Islamic rituals in Islam. This is because Muslims visit great and sacred places such as mosques and madrassas in order to perform Islamic rituals. Although the words "church" and "mosque" in both languages have the same function for the people, they have their usage functions. Here, people use a unique and appropriate term. That is why the word "church" is not used in the Uzbek version of the proverb. This means that lexemes that exist in the life of a nation and are actively used in everyday life create their image in the language and are involved in proverbs to reflect the national mentality of people. Focusing on the linguistic features of proverbs, of course, we cannot help but talk about the unique national character and mentality of nations. Folk proverbs, which concisely convey the culture, history, and traditions of the people, are at the forefront of expressing the mentality of the people. [3] In the following part of the thesis, analyzing the linguocultural features of some articles in English and Uzbek, we show the unique national traditions of both peoples and the expression of the specific national character in everyday life. We try to express the commonalities of the similarities by studying the more different aspects through a critical analysis of the proverbs in both languages. Proverbs are an invaluable example of folk art, reflecting the national and cultural characteristics of the people, their worldview, and the spirit of the nation. As the famous linguist Dal put it, "A collection of proverbs is a set of proverbs derived from the

language of the people, an experience, a set of common sense, a fact that people have learned in life." When it comes to articles in different languages, they speak the same language.

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